

one of the methods (Table 1) given in the experimental part. Amongst them are five new γ -keto acids (II 7, 9, 13, 18, 20) which were characterised by preparing their esters (Table 1) and infra-red spectroscopy (aromatic CO : 1675-1660, carboxyl CO : 1710-1690 cm^{-1}). The γ -aroylbutyric acids were subjected to Bucherer-Berg reaction to get γ -(5-arylhydantoin-5)-butyric acids (Fig. 1) which were identified by infrared spectroscopy⁸ (2-CO : 1710-1690 cm^{-1} , 4-CO : 1790-1775 cm^{-1} , carboxyl CO : 1740-1730 cm^{-1} , NH doublet : 3400-3180 cm^{-1}) and by preparing their esters (Table 1). The compounds were tested for antitubercular activity and all of them were found to be completely inactive.

It is evident from Table 1 that γ -aroylbutyric acids (II 17, 18, 20, 22, 23) having ortho substituents in aryl ring failed to give hydantoin derivatives. Again the failure is attributed to steric hindrance of ortho group as noticed earlier². Prolonged reaction time in the conversion of γ -(disubstituted aroyl) butyric acids into hydantoin derivatives was also observed.

Experimental

γ -Aroylbutyric acid (II)

Procedure A

γ -(*p*-Chlorobenzoyl)-butyric acid (II.7) : AlCl_3 (16 g) was gradually added to a cooled (0-5°) solution of glutaric anhydride (5.7 g, 0.05 *M*) in dry chlorobenzene (100 ml) over 1/2 hr, while the flask was swirled for proper mixing. Then the mixture was heated on steam bath until the evolution of HCl gas ceased. It was then cooled under tap and decomposed by ice and conc. HCl. Excess of chlorobenzene was removed in steam and the residue was digested with 10% solution of NaHCO_3 (100 ml). The cold aqueous filtrate was washed with ether and pure acid was precipitated from acidified aqueous layer, recrystallised from boiling water to get white needles, m.p. 121°, yield 7.4 g (65%) Me ester : m.p. 35°.

Procedure B

γ -(*p*-Ethylbenzoyl)-butyric acid (II.9) : Ethyl benzene (10.6 g, 0.1 *M*), nitrobenzene (10 ml), tetrachloroethane (15 ml) was cooled (0-5°) in a three necked 250 ml round bottom flask, equipped with a stirrer, dropping funnel, calcium chloride guard tube and a gas outlet tube. Powdered AlCl_3 (27 g, 0.2 *M*) was added to it. A solution of glutaric anhydride (11.4 g, 0.1 *M*) in 25 ml of tetrachloroethane was gradually added through the dropping funnel over 3/4 hr. with vigorous stirring. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr and worked up as described in procedure A. White needles m.p. 98°, yield 5.5 g (50%), Me ester : m.p. 40°.

γ -(5-Arylhantoin-5)-butyric acid(III)

Procedure C

γ -(5-phenylhydantoin-5)-butyric acid(III. 1) :

γ -Benzoyl-butyric acid(II. 1)(3.84 g, 0.02 *M*), potassium cyanide (3.25 g, 0.025 *M*), ammonium carbonate (7.68 g, 0.08 *M*) and water (50 ml) were mixed in a 100 ml round bottom flask fitted with an air condenser. The flask was warmed at 60° for 10 hr and at 85° for further 3 hr. It was then cooled under tap, acidified with dil. HCl and kept overnight. The white ppt. washed with water, recrystallised from boiling water gave white needles, m.p. 177.5°, yield 2.88 g (55%), Me ester : m.p. 133°.

Procedure D

γ -[5-(3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-hydantoin-5]-butyric acid(III. 11) : γ -(3-methyl-4-methoxy-phenyl) butyric acid(II. 11), (4.24 g, 0.02 *M*), potassium cyanide (3.25 g, 0.025 *M*), ammonium carbonate (7.68 g, 0.08 *M*) and water (50 ml) were mixed in a 100 ml round bottom flask, fitted with an air condenser. The flask was warmed at 60° for 15 hr and at 85° for further 5 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was acidified with dl. HCl. The overnight white ppt. when washed with water, recrystallised from boiling water gave white needles, m.p. 234°, yield 4.28 g (70%), Me ester : m.p. 183°.

Biological Tests

The hydantoin derivatives were screened against mycobacterium tuberculosis Var hominis H_{37}Rv_1 in Youman's medium. None of the compounds were found active.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. B. V. Bapat for kind co-operation.

References

1. R. N. DESHPANDE and K. S. NARGUND, *Indian J. Chem.* 1970, **8**, 1043.
2. A. N. KADAM, S. N. KULKARNI and B. B. GHATGE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (in Press)
3. H. M. RANDALL, R. G. FOWLER, N. FUSON and J. R. DANGAL, *Infra-red Determination of Organic Structures* (Van Nostrand, 1949).

Chemical Constituents of the Stem and Roots of *Xanthium strumarium* Linn

N. P. S. BISHT* and RANBIR SINGH**

Department of Chemistry, J. V. College, Baraut (Meerut)

Manuscript received 19 September 1977, revised 20 July 1978,
accepted 30 August 1978

XANTHIUM strumarium Linn (Compositae) is a medicinal plant and the roots are useful as bitter tonic, in strumous diseases and cancer¹. In our earlier reports^{2,3} we have investigated the leaves of this plant and the present paper is related to our findings on the stem and roots of *X. strumarium*.

* Address all correspondence to this author.

** Present address—Principal, Sri Aurabindo College, University of Delhi, Delhi.

The ethyl acetate extract of the stem yielded β -sitosterol and other unidentified minor constituents, while from the alcoholic extract KCl was obtained. The petroleum ether soluble part of the ethyl acetate extract of the roots yielded *n*-heptacosanol, β -sitosterol and stigmaterol while the petroleum ether insoluble part furnished 3, 4-dihydroxy cinnamic acid, β -sitosterol-D-glucoside and an uncharacterised chalcone derivative, m.p. 171-172°; the last two compounds were reported earlier from the leaves⁹. The 95% alcohol extract of the roots gave KCl, KNO₃ and K₂SO₄ and showed the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose (co-paper chromatography).

The compounds were identified by various spectral analyses, m.m.p., co-TLC and preparation of their derivatives.

Experimental

Ethyl acetate extract of Stem—The coarsely powdered stem (1 kg) was extracted with hot ethyl acetate (EtOAc) and the solvent removed. The residue was extracted with hot petroleum ether (60°-80°)(PE) under reflux and the concentrated extract was chromatographed over deactivated alumina with PE and its mixture with benzene (C₆H₆) in increasing proportions. The PE eluate and its mixture with C₆H₆ (3 : 1) eluate gave an unidentified waxy solid (25 mg) and a white solid (20 mg) respectively.

β -Sitosterol—The PE : C₆H₆ (1 : 1) eluate furnished a white solid which on repeated crystallisation from MeOH yielded β -sitosterol as colourless plates (420 mg), m.p. 137-138°; MS m/e 414(M⁺); acetate, m.p. 126-127° and benzoate, m.p. 145-146°.

Alcoholic extract of the defatted stem on concentration yielded KCl and analysed by flame photometry and usual methods of analysis. The chlorine content⁴ of the stem was 0.70%.

Ethyl acetate extract of Root—The coarsely powdered root (0.8 kg) was extracted with hot ethyl acetate and the residue, obtained after removal of the solvent, was divided into hot PE soluble and insoluble parts. The soluble part was concentrated and chromatographed (rechromatographed when necessary) over deactivated alumina with PE and its mixture with C₆H₆ in increasing proportions.

n-Heptacosanol—The PE eluate afforded *n*-heptacosanol⁶, crystallising from EtOH as colourless crystals (225 mg), m.p. 74-76° (IR and NMR) acetate, m.p. 61-64°.

β -Sitosterol—The PE : C₆H₆ (1 : 1) eluate afforded β -sitosterol (560 mg) crystallising from MeOH as colourless plates, m.p. 138°.

Stigmaterol—The white solid obtained from PE : C₆H₆ (1 : 1) eluates after rechromatography

and repeated crystallisation from C₆H₆ : MeOH (1 : 1) yielded stigmaterol as colourless needles (470 mg), m.p. 169-170°, (IR and NMR), (m/e 412, M⁺), acetate, m.p. 144° and benzoate, m.p. 158-159°.

The PE insoluble part was dissolved in hot MeOH and chromatographed over silica gel with EtOAc and its mixture with MeOH in increasing proportions as eluents.

3,4-Dihydroxy cinnamic acid—A yellow solid, obtained from EtOAc : MeOH (2 : 1) eluates, on crystallisation yielded 3, 4-dihydroxy cinnamic acid as yellow needles (595 mg), m.p. 195-196° (EtOAc : EtOH, 4 : 1). This acid was isolated from the alcoholic extract of the leaves⁸ of this plant.

β -Sitosterol-D-glucoside—A white solid, obtained from EtOAc : MeOH (1 : 2) eluate fractions gave β -sitosterol-D-glucoside, crystallising from Pyr.-EtOH mixture as colourless plates (710 mg), m.p. 288-290°.

An uncharacterised chalcone derivative⁸ was obtained as yellow needles (550 mg), m.p. 171-172° from EtOAc : MeOH (1 : 5) eluate fractions.

Alcoholic extract of the defatted roots—were extracted with 95% alcohol and the cold concentrated extract afforded KCl, KNO₃ and K₂SO₄, identified by flame photometry and usual methods of analysis. The chlorine content of the roots was found to be 0.29%. The inorganic salts free filtrate was treated with excess of water when a viscous semisolid separated out and attempts to crystallise it failed. The aqueous solution was reduced to a syrup which gave positive Molisch test for carbohydrates. Ascending paper chromatography⁸ revealed the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose, supported by co-paper chromatography with pure specimens.

Acknowledgement

Authors' thanks are due to the authorities of J. V. College, Baraut for providing necessary facilities and to Drs. R. K. Bansal and Pahup Singh for valuable suggestions. Our thanks are also due to the Director, CDRI, Lucknow for analysis and UGC for financial assistance.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAVAR and I. C. CHOPRA : *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*, CSIR, New Delhi, 1956, p. 269.
2. N. P. S. BISHT and RANBIR SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 797.
3. N. P. S. BISHT and RANBIR SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 707.
4. K. PAECH and M. V. TRACEY ; *Modern Methods of Plant Analysis*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1955, Vol. 1, p. 487.
5. H. EL. KHADEM and N. M. A. RAHMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 3488.